

Langemeyer, I. (2019). Developments of work and VET through the transitions of the energy sector. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.384-389) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641758>

Developments of work and VET through the transitions of the energy sector

Langemeyer, Ines

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, ines.langemeyer@kit.edu

Abstract

The planned comprehensive use of solar energy and windmill power plants etc. as sustainable energies raises the question how the energy system (power grids e.g.) shall be transformed and how smart technologies support systems that balance and coordinate between uneven power generation and consumption. Simulations and test sites as they are run by larger units of researchers at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology give an account of relevant transformations concerning work and education as well. The paper deals with sociological and educational aspects how working and learning is influenced. One aspect of this development is the world-changing character of scientific inventions such as artificial intelligence and ‘deep learning’, through which more and more dimensions of societal life become dependent on scientifically invented technologies. As this brings about new problems of safety, quality and control, the scientification of work is scrutinized.

Keywords

modelling; energy transition; scientification of work

1 Social-science Research on Energy Transition and Modeling

After the disaster of the reactor in Fukushima, the German government decided to shut down nuclear energy by 2022 and to maintain thereupon the entire energy supply with sustainable energies. Today, this enterprise of the energy transition still requires a lot of research: How can power grids be transformed and how can ‘smart’ technologies support systems to balance and coordinate between uneven power generation and consumption, hence solar energy and windmill power plants etc. generate fluctuating amounts of energy. Simulations and test sites as they are run by larger units of researchers at the KIT give an account of relevant transformations concerning work and education as well.

The research project “Poetic Modelling and Energy Transition”¹ relates to the facets and the roles of models and modelling for the success of the ecological and political aims to foster sustainability not only in terms of the technological power generation but also societally, as shifts in societal life are inevitable. The energy transition is therefore a socio-technological enterprise with high significance for numerous concomitant developments in the future.

¹ This project is funded from 2017 to 2021 by the VW-Stiftung within the framework “Extraordinary Projects” (<http://portal.volkswagenstiftung.de/search/projectPDF.do?projectId=8722>)

My paper deals with sociological and educational aspects as to how working and learning is influenced. Its aim is to outline a critical research program which:

- Clarifies more general questions concerning the scientification of work,
- Is empirically based research on pedagogical aspects as to how learning and teaching critical thinking can contribute to a critical practice with models, and
- Discusses risks and potentials of further developments, e.g. how we want to live and how democracy can be realized within socio-technological projects such as the energy transition.

2 Scientification of work and its relation to the energy transition project

Scientification is understood as a rather precarious process of the non-simultaneous and non-linear *individual and cultural* human development, often entangled with many contradictions (cf. Langemeyer, 2015; 2017; 2019). One aspect of this is the world-changing character of scientific inventions such as artificial intelligence, through which more and more dimensions of societal life become dependent on scientifically invented technologies. Its world-changing character does not concern the built environment only. However, with regard to the planned energy transition, ‘smart’ grids, ‘smart’ houses and ‘smart’ cities are major visions to solve the problems of great variabilities in energy production and energy consumption.

A concomitant aspect of this transition is the development of labor. Regarding demands to qualification, the scientification process is not necessarily clear or unambiguous: There is no automatism and no guarantee that the individual worker becomes a scientist just because technologies are produced scientifically. However, depending on the digitalization and the automation of processes that formerly required manual labor, main aspects of the scientification of work lie in the intellectualization of processes and procedures (i.e. relevant intervention into digitalized processes is possible only via using computers and scientific methods etc.).

‘Scientification’ concerns the numerous relations that individuals as well as organisations need to maintain with scientific knowledge, as it contributes to higher productivity or creates new societal uses.

Institutions like the university and higher education play an important role in the long-term societal process of scientification which changes e.g. the mode of production and the entire societal exchange. Thus, two sides of science co-evolve: Scientification is, on the one hand, a material process to institutionalize certain scientific practices affirming certain pieces of approved knowledge as achievements to objective truth, certainty, and common acknowledgement of expectations (such as accepted standards). In sum, this means that these stores of knowledge become societally relevant, applicable or usable by a relevant quantity of worker and, last but not least, usable for different purposes. The ‘institutionalization’ of science is not only important within the societal organization to further scientific research. It contributes also to stability and efficacy in society, to the development of forces of production, and, reciprocally, to the reputation of scientific institutions, titles, proficiency and expertise. In other words, this process is simultaneously about forming societal practice through scientific expertise. It supports the relevance and the influence of universities as well as research institutions. Scientists who belong to this science system participate in organizing the disposal over resources as well as opportunities to influence people’s opinions and the formation of their worldview(s).

However, on the other hand, the process of scientification must be understood as a process of radically doubting and criticizing, and thus even as an effort of breaking away from

established forms of scientific societal practice, technologies, ethics, worldviews, paradigms and, of reorganizing science and the field of power structures (Langemeyer, 2015, ch. 4).

With regard to the planned energy transition, both aspects, the institutionalization of science and the radical critique of the scientification tendency become relevant. Replacing the old, basically nuclear energy supply by a renewable and sustainable energy supply means a radical critique of established forms and standards, given infrastructures and long-time beliefs.

But at the same time new models, standards, beliefs and infrastructures must be established. This necessarily entangles greater tensions and struggles of power over resources in the science system and beyond. As the industry and other sectors of the economy play a major role for the energy transition project, the interdependence between the science system and the economy comes to the fore. Joint ventures of research institutions and private companies with subsidies by the government are often the basis for development.

3 Empirical research into the scientification of work

Before I give a summary of insights gained by interviews with researchers at the KIT, I report how the scientification of work can be studied empirically and more generally by socio-demographic and socio-economic statistics. The labor market changed in the past decades. A study by the IAB (German institute for labor market and vocation related research) shows that vocations and professions are changing.

Figure 1 Increase and decrease in jobs in different sectors of the German economy from 1996 until 2013 (Wolter et al., 2016)

The future prospects predicted in this study by Wolter et al. (2016) consider major changes in levels of qualification demands. Low-skilled jobs with ancillary activities (“Helfertätigkeiten”) as well as technical or functional jobs (“fachliche Tätigkeiten”) will diminish while complex work activities (“komplexe Tätigkeiten”) and highly complex work activities (“hochkomplexe Tätigkeiten”) will likely increase (see fig. 2).

Figure 2 Increase and decrease in future qualification levels (Wolter et al., 2016)

The analysis (fig. 1) gives evidence that a larger increase of jobs occurred in the sector of health care, IT-work and natural science-related professions, and especially in the sector of media, humanities and social sciences-related professions while the number of jobs in non-skilled or low-skilled sectors decreased and will probably continue to decrease (fig. 2). Against this background, I conducted together with my colleague, Andreas Martin, research on the basis of the German microcensus (Langemeyer/Martin, 2018). The microcensus-data allows running a cluster analysis on job characteristics. By distinguishing between the frequency of academic titles/degrees and the density of disciplines in the various vocational domains, the following seven clusters can be identified:

Figure 3 Cluster-analysis of the academization in distinction to the scientification of the labor market in Germany, microcensus 2015 (Langemeyer/Martin, 2018)

As one can see in fig. 3 with this cluster analysis, it is important to differentiate the role of higher education for the labor market. There are vocational domains like the classic professions that strictly require certain academic degrees, e.g.: Becoming a physician is still a highly regulated career so that the density of people with medical education and the frequency of academic titles is both high. However, there are other areas of the labor market where employees dispose of an academic title but their education is not homogeneous. Instead, a variety of disciplines prevail in that area. This means that these careers are less regulated and that academic education is important because general capacities of scientific thinking are relevant. We assume that this indicates certain domains where problem solving or mediation between different disciplines and expertise have become a relevant aspect of working life (Lange-meyer/Martin, 2018). This gives simultaneously evidence for the scientification of work. Analyses of workplace studies in the IT-sector and surgery provide further evidence that complex and even highly complex work activities have emerged (Langemeyer 2015; 2019).

4 Uncertainties concerning the energy transition – insights from an interview study

At the KIT, seven interviews for investigating the academic side of the energy transition were conducted with researchers from different fields. More interviews are planned. Insights to this research are summarized as follows:

The energy transition project is huge and complex process, but there are no detailed descriptions and agreements of how and when solutions will be ready to hand and implemented in a secure and reasonable way.

Researchers (like those interviewed at the KIT) try to contribute with their research activities to solutions, mostly within predefined frameworks. But it is uncertain whether these frameworks and the research accomplished will be relevant and pathbreaking within the entire societal project. Decisions about setting up a certain framework depend e.g. on the data that is available or the time one can use to conduct research (as research funding ends within a certain period, as industry partners set up time-frames, or as doctoral students get a fixed-term contract).

The different uncertainties are thus not only research-driven (as knowledge production is always contingent). It is also due to the unclear goals to be reached and undefined criteria to be met. Another aspect of this uncertainty is that a change in the energy supply and the used infrastructure affects the entire society and international relations. The energy transition will be an all-encompassing restructuring of economic and political interdependencies. Public awareness for this aspect is probably still pretty low. There is no dissemination of information about what consequences the energy transition will possibly bring about to our way of life. Consequently, public discussions are rarely. Sufficient insight for the public is not provided.

However, this circumstance requires another type of research around the energy transition that is not merely technology-related. Especially, researchers with a special focus on economic aspects do not see the energy transition as a technological experiment only. They pay attention to political and societal problems that are entangled and unfold with changes of the energy sector as well. Questions arise about how markets will work when the electric power-trading is organized in more flexible ways. One concern is about how the population would react if more detailed information should be made available about their use of energy and their way of living, consuming and working. Another aspect is whether markets would work if people would advance from power consumers to power traders, since a greater part of the population might own solar energy plants and/or store temporarily energy in batteries, for example. Since the disposability of electric power could decrease depending on weather and consumption, solutions need to be modelled which energy use has priority and which has not. Especially this question of cutting and down-sizing energy use makes it clear that deep changes of societal life are likely and call for dealing with them in advance.

Large parts of the research in the energy sector is therefore based on modelling. However, the numerous models used are not compatible. Insights gained by using simulations and by calculating certain models cannot be accumulated. The question arises whether narratives told around modelling compensate the lack of coherence and rationality.

References

- Langemeyer, I. (2015). *Das Wissen der Achtsamkeit. Kooperative Kompetenz in komplexen Arbeitsprozessen*. Münster: Waxmann.
- Langemeyer, I. (2017). Methodological Challenges of Investigating Intellectual Cooperation, Relational Expertise, and Transformative Agency. *Nordic Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 7(2), 39-62.
- Langemeyer, I. (2019). *Digitalisierung als Herausforderung für Personalentwicklung und Mitbestimmung. Unternehmensstrategien der IT-Branche und ihre Bedeutung für Weiterbildung*. Opladen: Verlag Barbara Budrich.
- Langemeyer, I./Martin, A. (2018): Akademiker*innen ohne Professionsstatus? – Oder: Wie Wissenschaft in die Gesellschaft kommt und was dies für das Studium bedeutet. In: bwp@Berufs- und Wirtschaftspädagogik – online, Ausgabe 34, 1-20. http://www.bwpat.de/ausgabe34/langemeyer_martin_bwpat34.pdf
- Wolter, I. et al. (2016): IAB-Forschungsbericht 13/2016: Wirtschaft 4.0 und die Folgen für Arbeitsmarkt und Ökonomie. Szenario-Rechnungen im Rahmen der BIBB-IAB-Qualifikations- und Berufsfeldprojektionen

Biographical notes

Dr Ines Langemeyer is a Professor for science education at the institute for vocational education and the philosophy of education at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. She obtained a Diplom in psychology at the Free University of Berlin and a PhD at the Helmut-Schmidt-University in Hamburg.